

On Colloidal Electrolytes : An Attempt to Find the Dissociation Constant of Pectinic Acid

B. N. GHOSH

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-9.

Manuscript received 5 January 1976 ; revised 22 March 1976 ; accepted 8 April 1976.

It has been shown that the values of pH of samples of pectinic acid of different CH_3O content calculated by using an equation deduced by the author agree well with those observed by Speiser, Hills and Eddy. Of one sample only (no. H 91 E) of low CH_3O content (viz. 1.70 per cent, $\Gamma=0.90$) three different concentrations have been used for titration. From the titration data of this sample (no. H 91E) its (dissociation constant) pK_s has been found to be 3.41 which is independent of the concentration of the acid and its degree of neutralisation, α . As this K_s of pectinic acid of low ester content, agrees well with the intrinsic dissociation constant K_a of galacturonic acid ($pK_a = 3.42$), so it has been concluded that it (i.e. K_s) is identical with the intrinsic dissociation constant K_a of (de-esterified) pectinic acid also.

THE behaviour of natural and synthetic polyacids like gum arabic acid, pectinic acid and polyacrylic acids during titration and dilution has been extensively investigated both theoretically¹⁻⁴ and experimentally⁵⁻¹⁰. The results of these investigations show that their dissociation constants vary with their degree of neutralisation α , with their concentration C , and with the concentration of an added neutral salt. In previous papers¹²⁻¹⁴ this author has shown that the variation with dilution of the H^+ ion activity H_c of the colloidal acids, purified properly by dialysis, can be accounted for by the following equation

$$H_c = \theta H_s + (1-\theta)H_t \quad \dots (1)$$

where θ represents the fraction per unit area of the surface of the hydrogen electrode covered by the diffuse double layers of the macromolecules of the acid and $\theta = C/(K_0+C)$, C being the concentration of the acid and K_0 , a constant. H_s is a proportionality constant and may be interpreted to represent the H^+ ion activity associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the electrode and H_t the H^+ ion activity of the intermicellar solution. It may be pointed out that when purified colloidal acids are diluted with water, C and hence θ vary, but H_s and H_t remain constant (vide papers¹²⁻¹⁴).

When θ is fairly large and the colloidal acid has been properly purified by dialysis $(1-\theta)H_t$ is quite small and can be neglected and equation (1) can then be written as follows :

$$H_c = \theta H_s \quad \dots (2)$$

At constant C equation (2) can be applied to potentiometric titration data. As C is constant, so θ remains constant during titration, but H_s decreases as α

increases. Since H_s may be different from H_a defined by the Henderson equation, $H_a = K_a(1-\alpha)/\alpha$ in which the ratio of the activity coefficients f_A and f_B of the COOH and COO^- groups respectively has been taken as unity, so it has been assumed in a previous paper¹⁵ that $H_s = K'(H_a)^n = K'(K_a)^n[(1-\alpha)/\alpha]^n$ where K_a is the intrinsic dissociation constant of the COOH group, α the degree of neutralisation, K' and n are constants and $n > 1$. Substituting this last value of H_s in equation (2) and simplifying the following equation is obtained

$$pH_c = p(\theta K_s) + n \log \alpha/(1-\alpha) \quad \dots (3)$$

where $K_s = K'(K_a)^n$. It is to be noted that K_s becomes equal to K_a when $K'(K_a)^{n-1} = 1$.

It may be pointed out that an equation similar to (3) can also be deduced by modifying the assumptions in the following way. Let us now assume that

$$\begin{aligned} H_s &= (H_a)f_A/f_B = K_a[(1-\alpha)/\alpha]f_A/f_B \\ &= K_a[(1-\alpha)/\alpha] \times [(1-\alpha)/\alpha]^x \quad \dots (3a) \end{aligned}$$

where the ratio of the activity coefficients is not unity, but a function of $(1-\alpha)/\alpha$, the form of which as assumed above is $f_A/f_B = [(1-\alpha)/\alpha]^x$, x remaining constant over a certain range of values of α . In a macromolecule, say of pectinic acid, containing p groups of COOH , as the degree of neutralisation α increases, the electrical charge of the macromolecule increases and owing to increased electrostatic attraction the ability of each of the remaining $p(1-\alpha)$ groups of COOH to release a proton decreases and the ability of each of the $p\alpha$ groups of COO^- to bind a proton increases. Therefore, it has been assumed that the ratio of the activity coefficients f_A/f_B varies in the way indicated above. Substituting

$K_a[(1-\alpha)/\alpha]^{1+x}$ for H_s in equation (2) and converting it into the logarithmic form the following equation is obtained

$$pH_c = p(\theta K_a) + (1+x)[\log \alpha/(1-\alpha)] \quad \dots (4)$$

A comparison of the equations (3) and (4) leads to the conclusion that if both of them represent the titration curve of a particular colloidal acid of given concentration then the following conditions are to be satisfied, $n = 1+x$ and $K_s = K_a$. It has already been pointed out that $n > 1$ and that K_s becomes equal to K_a when $K'(K_a)^{n-1} = 1$. Experimental data recorded in the paper will show how far the aforesaid conditions are satisfied.

Speiser, Hills and Eddy⁷ have prepared samples of low ash content pectinic acid (from apple pectin)

containing various proportions of methoxyl groups by acid and enzymatic de-esterification and have made a comparative study of their acid behaviour by potentiometric titration. The ratio of the number of COOH groups in the system to the total number of galacturonide residue denoted by Γ has been calculated by them from the following relation

$$\Gamma = \frac{\text{COOH}}{\text{COOH} + \text{COOCH}_3} = \frac{N/M}{N/M + \text{CH}_3\text{O}/3100} \quad \dots (5)$$

where N represents the total concentration of carboxyl groups per litre, M the concentration of pectinic acid in grams per liter, CH_3O is the methoxyl content expressed in per cent by weight of solid and 31 is the molecular weight of the CH_3O residue. Their data are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE 1(a). TITRATION DATA OF ACID DE-ESTERIFIED PECTINIC ACID, SAMPLE NO. H91E

$\Gamma = 0.90$, ash content = 0.53 per cent, $p(\theta K_s) = 4.40$.

C	α	$\log \alpha/(1-\alpha)$	n	Values of pH	
				Observed	Calculated from eqn. (3)
4.15×10^{-3}	0.204	-0.59	2.2	3.11	3.10
"	0.237	-0.51	2.2	3.28	3.28
"	0.282	-0.41	2.2	3.50	3.50
"	0.342	-0.28	2.2	3.78	3.78
"	0.418	-0.143	2.2	4.04	4.08
"	0.594	+0.165	1.3	4.57	4.61
"	0.780	+0.55	1.3	5.14	5.12
"	0.874	+0.84	1.3	5.52	5.49

TABLE 1(b). TITRATION DATA OF ACID DE-ESTERIFIED PECTINIC ACID, SAMPLE NO. H91E

$\Gamma = 0.90$, ash content = 0.53 per cent, $p(\theta K_s) = 4.14$

C	α	$\log \alpha/(1-\alpha)$	n	Values of pH	
				Observed	Calculated from eqn. (3)
8.35×10^{-3}	0.212	-0.570	1.76	3.07	3.14
"	0.259	-0.456	1.76	3.35	3.34
"	0.328	-0.312	1.76	3.64	3.59
"	0.411	-0.156	1.76	3.89	3.87
"	0.683	+0.33	1.40	4.61	4.60
"	0.776	+0.54	1.40	4.90	4.90
"	0.870	+0.82	1.40	5.31	5.29

TABLE 1(c). TITRATION DATA OF ACID DE-ESTERIFIED PECTINIC ACID, SAMPLE NO. H91E

$\Gamma = 0.90$, ash content = 0.53 per cent, $p(\theta K_s) = 3.91$

C	α	$\log \alpha/(1-\alpha)$	n	Values of pH	
				Observed	Calculated from eqn. (3)
16.82×10^{-3}	0.164	-0.91	1.6	2.77	2.77
"	0.186	-0.64	1.6	2.90	2.89
"	0.215	-0.56	1.6	3.02	3.01
"	0.247	-0.48	1.6	3.16	3.14
"	0.499	-0.002	1.3	3.93	3.91
"	0.907	+0.99	1.3	5.22	5.20

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TABLE 2. TITRATION DATA OF ACID DE-ESTERIFIED PECTINIC ACID ; SAMPLE NO. H91B

$\Gamma = 0.56$, ash content = 0.24 per cent, $p(\theta K_s) = 3.93$.

C	α	$\log \alpha/(1-\alpha)$	n	Values of pH	
				Observed	Calculated from eqn. (3)
5.19×10^{-3}	0.233	-0.517	1.9	2.94	2.95
"	0.258	-0.459	1.9	3.06	3.06
"	0.289	-0.391	1.9	3.20	3.19
"	0.328	-0.312	1.9	3.36	3.34
"	0.377	-0.218	1.9	3.53	3.52
"	0.435	-0.113	1.9	3.70	3.71
"	0.499	-0.0017	1.9	3.88	3.93
"	0.566	+0.115	1.4	4.12	4.09
"	0.637	+0.244	1.4	4.28	4.27
"	0.710	+0.389	1.4	4.49	4.48
"	0.860	+0.788	1.4	4.94	5.03
"	0.935	+1.158	1.4	5.55	5.55

TABLE 3. TITRATION DATA OF ENZYME DE-ESTERIFIED PECTINIC ACID ; SAMPLE NO. H91H

$\Gamma = 0.67$, ash content = 0.55 per cent, $p(\theta K_s) = 4.03$

C	α	$\log \alpha/(1-\alpha)$	n	Values of pH	
				Observed	Calculated from eqn. (3)
5.64×10^{-3}	0.248	-0.48	2.0	3.09	3.07
"	0.280	-0.41	2.0	3.22	3.21
"	0.319	-0.33	2.0	3.38	3.37
"	0.365	-0.24	2.0	3.55	3.55
"	0.608	+0.19	1.4	4.30	4.30
"	0.744	+0.46	1.4	4.69	4.67
"	0.883	+0.88	1.4	5.27	5.26

TABLE 4. TITRATION DATA OF ENZYME DE-ESTERIFIED PECTINIC ACID : SAMPLE NO. H91J

$\Gamma = 0.86$, ash content = 1.01 per cent, $p(\theta K_s) = 4.13$

C	α	$\log \alpha/(1-\alpha)$	n	Values of pH	
				Observed	Calculated from eqn. (3)
6.98×10^{-3}	0.216	-0.560	1.7	3.11	3.18
"	0.243	-0.500	1.7	3.25	3.28
"	0.275	-0.421	1.7	3.41	3.41
"	0.315	-0.337	1.7	3.58	3.56
"	0.361	-0.248	1.7	3.74	3.71
"	0.464	-0.158	1.7	3.88	3.86
"	0.517	+0.030	1.4	4.16	4.17
"	0.569	+0.121	1.4	4.30	4.30
"	0.619	+0.211	1.4	4.46	4.43
"	0.682	+0.331	1.4	4.60	4.59
"	0.849	+0.750	1.4	5.16	5.18

TABLE 5. pK_s VALUES OF PECTINIC ACIDS DE-ESTERIFIED TO DIFFERENT EXTENT

K_0 (IN θ) = 36.57×10^{-3}

De-esterified by	Γ	C	θ	$p(\theta K_s)$	pK_s
acid	0.90	4.15×10^{-3}	0.102	4.40	3.41
"	0.90	8.35×10^{-3}	0.186	4.14	3.41
"	0.90	16.82×10^{-3}	0.315	3.91	3.41
"	0.56	5.19×10^{-3}	0.124	3.93	3.02
enzyme	0.67	5.64×10^{-3}	0.134	4.03	3.16
"	0.86	6.98×10^{-3}	0.160	4.13	3.33

Notes on the data recorded in the Tables 1-5

The titration of the different samples of pectinic acid has been done by the potentiometric method by Speiser, Hills and Eddy⁷ at 27°. In the Tables *C* denotes the concentration of pectinic acid in gram equivalents per liter. The other terms have the same significance as explained already. The value of $p(\theta K_s)$ in each case has been found by plotting pH as ordinate and $\log \alpha/(1-\alpha)$ as abscissa. The intercept on the ordinate, corresponding to $\log \alpha/(1-\alpha) = 0$, gives the value of $p(\theta K_s)$. Since three different concentrations of the same sample H 91 E have been used for titration, there are three different values of (θK_s) in which K_s is constant but θ varies. Taking their ratio, two at a time, three ratios are obtained from which K_s has been eliminated. As *C* is known the value of K_0 in θ^* can easily be found from each of these three ratios. The values of K_0 thus found are 36.7×10^{-3} , 36.7×10^{-3} and 36.3×10^{-3} and their average 36.57×10^{-3} has been used for calculation of the data in Table 5.

Discussion

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Tables 1-4, that for different values of α , the values of pH calculated from equation (3) agree well with those observed. The value of n below $\alpha = 0.5$ is always higher than that above $\alpha = 0.5$, but in each case it is greater than unity and remains constant over a certain range of α .

The data recorded in the Tables 1(a) to 1(c) of sample no. H 91 E show that as the concentration of pectinic acid is increased the value of $p(\theta K_s)$ decreases although for each concentration $p(\theta K_s)$ is constant and independent of α within the range investigated.

Furthermore, it appears from the data in the Tables 1(b), 2, 3 and 4 that as Γ increases the values of $p(\theta K_s)$ also increases. This means that at comparable concentrations the strength of the acid increases as its ester content increases. This fact has been noted by Speiser, Hills and Eddy.⁷

The values of $p(\theta K_s)$ found from the titration data by using equation (3) are summarised along with other necessary data in Table 5. Three concentrations of pectinic acid sample no. H 91 E, the ester content of which is quite small ($\Gamma = 0.90$), have been used for titration. The values of θ for these three concentrations have been calculated using the average value of $K_0 = 36.57 \times 10^{-3}$ found in the way explained already and are recorded in Table 5. The $p(\theta)$ of each of them has been calculated and the difference from the corresponding $p(\theta K_s)$ gives the

$$* \theta = C/(K_0 + C)$$

pK_s values. It will be noticed that for the three concentrations, pK_s has got the same value 3.41. It may be mentioned that pK_a of galacturonic acid determined by Speiser, Hills and Eddy⁷ is 3.42 at 27° and that by Karrar and Schwarzenbach¹⁶ at 23.6° is 3.49. Therefore, it may be concluded from the experimental results that pK_s of pectinic acid (de-esterified nearly completely) is the same as the pK_a of galacturonic and pectinic acids. Since $pK_s = pK_a$, therefore, it follows from what has been discussed already that $K'(K_a)^{n-1} = 1$ or if n is put equal to $1 + \alpha$ then $K'(K_a)^\alpha = 1$. Therefore, for the determination of pK_a of colloidal acids from potentiometric titration data equation (4) can be used directly.

Of the other samples of pectinic acid H 91 B, H 91 H and H 91 J only one concentration in each case has been used for titration. Therefore, K_0 in these cases cannot be found and so the actual values of θ of these samples cannot be calculated. However, assuming $K_0 = 36.57 \times 10^{-3}$ in these cases also, tentative values of pK_s have been calculated. It will be noticed that the values of pK_s of these samples of acid diminish as the values of Γ diminish (i.e., as the ester content increases). This is in agreement with theory¹⁷; as for example, in a monoester of phosphoric acid the dissociation constants of the other two ionisable H atoms are appreciably greater than those of phosphoric acid.

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